

CULTUROLOGY

NATIONAL MUSEUMS IN THE INTERNATIONAL CULTURAL COOPERATION OF AZERBAIJAN

Guliyeva L.

Baku Slavic University, Doctor of Philosophy, Associate Professor

Abstract

Azerbaijan Museums of Azerbaijan have passed the big historical way of development. Museums of Azerbaijan are means of maintenance of the International cooperation in culture sphere. Activity of museums - one of forms of the international cultural relations. Cooperation of museums of Azerbaijan with museums of the countries is the mutual understanding and friendship's factor between the people.

Keywords: culture, museums, Azerbaijan.

Azerbaijan's museums have gone through a long historical development path. Starting from the end of the nineteenth century (the first museum was a school museum in the village of Nekhreme) to the present, the museums of Azerbaijan have become not only the pride of national culture, but also a means of ensuring international cooperation in the field of culture [14].

In 1992, the Azerbaijan National Committee of ICOM was established, which has been actively involved in the life of the museum community ever since. The Chairman and members of the ICOM National Committee take part in meetings of the ICOM Executive Committee, make presentations at international conferences of ICOM committees on the profile; several issues of the ICOM-Azerbaijan bulletin have been published [12].

The activity of museums with international aspects is one of the forms of international cultural relations. The modern Museum is an institution of civil society, it determines the level of self-identity of the nation, creates a close connection between the current state of society and the traditions of the people. This is especially important in the context of globalization [9, p.281]. Activities in the field of museums are an integral part of international cultural cooperation. The declaration, signed in 2002 by representatives of eighteen major museums in seven countries, states that "museums serve the citizens of not only one country, but all countries". The museum as an institution of civil society influences the mass consciousness [3, p.14-16]. This is especially important in the context of globalization. Museums are able to participate in shaping public opinion in various regions and countries of the world. International exhibitions are forms of direct cultural dialogue between peoples. They influence public opinion and are therefore one of the factors determining the state of international relations. The museum exhibition is a visual demonstration of political symbols, signs, including in the international sphere [6, p.18-19].

An art or historical museum ceases to be associated in the public consciousness with an elite and very small stratum of society. Two phenomena are changing the social significance of modern museums [2]. The first of them is mass tourism, which introduces millions of people to the masterpieces of world civilizations. The second factor is related to the specifics of modern mass media. The international exhibition is an obliga-

tory object of attention of television programs, newspapers and magazines not only in Azerbaijan, but also in the world as a whole. Moreover, the museum's opening day is traditionally interpreted in the media as "good news", which is so rare in the general flow of reports about the economic crisis, terrorism, and violence. This is how a positive image of the museum as a phenomenon of modern culture is justifiably formed. Posters announcing international exhibitions are visible in the historical centers of cities around the world, and magazines and newspapers report on exhibitions. Therefore, the information impact of the museum extends to a very wide audience [5].

It should be noted that all over the world, for a tourist or a viewer of a television program, a monument of history and culture displayed in a museum acquires the significance of a cultural symbol and sign, rather than an object of close study and comprehension. Thanks to the development of the Internet, museums are able to bring knowledge about world art to millions of people around the world [7, 2001].

The international museum system, of which the museums of Azerbaijan are an integral part, strives for cultural intervention in the broadest strata of modern society. One example of the global professional community's search for a new language is the centers of education and scientific work. The cooperation of Azerbaijani museums with museums of various countries of the world is a factor of mutual understanding, promotion of a culture of peace and friendship between peoples and states. Museum exhibitions accompany state visits of heads of state and high-level meetings.

The museum becomes a place of diplomatic interaction [8, p.36]. The activities of museums are often at the center of active diplomacy. The International Council of Museums (ICOM) is an international center for solving professional problems of the contemporary museum community. This organization was established in 1946 in the context of a broad international movement to create a more humane world. Today it unites 21,000 specialists from 146 countries around the world. It includes 30 international committees [7, 2003]. Among them is the association of museums dedicated to state crimes and museums of military history. The ICOM Code has been translated into dozens of languages. This document promotes the ideas of humanism and the protection of cultural human rights. In accordance with the Statute in the field of international cooperation, ICOM

strives to: promote the development of museum business worldwide; participate in the preservation of heritage and the fight against the prohibited trade in cultural property; establish cooperation between museum institutions and specialists from different countries [7, 2010].

ICOM strives to establish partnerships between museums of Azerbaijan and foreign countries with large collections. ICOM promotes the practical application of Azerbaijani legislation, according to which the country from which the work of art was illegally exported may impose a ban on its sale on the territory of Azerbaijan [14].

A characteristic feature of modernity is the desire to develop uniform standards of professional activity in different countries. ICOM promotes the professional training of museum workers in Azerbaijan in order to ensure the preservation and effective use of the cultural heritage of mankind. The ICOM Code of Museum Ethics is the most authoritative set of rules of professional conduct, which is recognized in Azerbaijan [12].

There are currently 146 museums and 30 art galleries in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Of the 146 museums, 138 (including 21 branches) are subordinate to the Ministry of Culture, 4 museums are subordinate to the National Academy of Sciences, and the rest are museums of other departments. The main museum collection consists of 1,150,936 exhibits [14].

The main major museums that actively participate in the process of international cultural cooperation, both on a bilateral basis and within the framework of UNESCO and ICOM are:

- Azerbaijan State Museum of Art named after R.Mustafayev (14,525 exhibits of the main collection)
- The State Museum of Azerbaijani Carpet and Applied Arts (9823 exhibits of the main fund)
- Azerbaijan State Museum of History (255375 exhibits of the main fund)
- State Architectural Historical and Memorial Complex of the Shirvanshahs Palace (21391 exhibits of the main fund)
- Azerbaijan State Theater Museum named after J.Jabbarli (116783 exhibits of the main fund)
- Azerbaijan State Museum of Musical Culture (31284 exhibits of the main fund)
- Azerbaijan State Museum of Literature named after Nizami (59275 exhibits of the main fund)

In total, 2,228 people work in the museums of Azerbaijan. Of these, 900 people are keepers, researchers, and guides [14].

The Ministry of Culture of Azerbaijan and the National Committee of ICOM have repeatedly raised with UNESCO the issue of the fate of the museums remaining in the occupied territories and their exhibits.

As a result, two UNESCO missions were sent to Azerbaijan to study this problem (1994, 1995), which resulted in an appeal signed by UNESCO's Deputy Director General calling for the protection of cultural values of the occupied lands. Also, with the assistance of UNESCO, a special edition was released with images and information about some of the seized museum valuables [15].

By developing international cooperation in the field of culture, and in particular in the field of museum cooperation, Azerbaijan strives to create conditions for the restoration of national historical monuments and cultural centers [4]. According to A. Garayev, the country's Minister of Culture and Tourism, Azerbaijan has never considered Karabakh and other occupied areas outside of national and international cultural projects [13]. When the tourist zones of Azerbaijan were defined, Karabakh and the occupied areas were approved as a special zone. According to the Azerbaijani government, museums, exhibits, monuments of Azerbaijani history, mosques, places of worship, architectural examples, and cultural centers in Karabakh are in poor condition. It is likely that the analysis of all this will take some time, but only after that Azerbaijan will decide what work will need to be carried out in the region. It is after this analysis that it should be determined which of the Azerbaijani cultural and historical monuments require restoration and which require reconstruction. The Azerbaijani government has fairly complete information about the condition of these monuments, including the museum, and has also determined the direction in which the state and international cultural policy in this area should be implemented. However, it is difficult to talk about serious training without real facts. According to A.Garayev, "there is a preliminary plan, this plan always exists, and we observe it daily. After the conclusion of a political agreement, architects and specialists in the protection of historical monuments of Azerbaijan will have their say" [13].

The Azerbaijani side has always sought to develop cooperation with international organizations in the field of museum business, especially UNESCO, ICOM, and the Council of Europe. The issue of Karabakh museums forms the basis of this cooperation [2, p. 69]. But, for some reason, the planned visit of the UNESCO fact-finding mission to Nagorno-Karabakh, as well as the Commission on Science, Education and Culture of the Council of Europe, will not take place. In 2006, an agreement was reached on the organization of the UNESCO mission. Azerbaijan has been expecting the visit of this mission for four years, but the visit has been postponed under various pretexts. Every time the Secretaries General of UNESCO and the Council of Europe come here, the Azerbaijani side asks them this question. Azerbaijan is interested in the visit taking place, and it would not be related to the general course of the peace process on the Karabakh issue [1]. Probably, the opposite side, being well aware of the situation, does not want to show the real picture and, under all sorts of political pretexts, makes it difficult for the mission to arrive. Of course, international organizations such as UNESCO, the Council of Europe, ICOM, and the OSCE must make a strong-willed decision, taking into account the norms and principles of international humanitarian law. The Azerbaijani side has prepared materials and documents that have been submitted to international organizations. Work has already begun with some experts from the commission of these bodies. Azerbaijan expected the arrival of the UNESCO and Council of Europe missions in 2008, 2009, and

2010, but unfortunately this visit did not take place. According to A.Garayev, "the issue can be resolved only and only after the signing of a political agreement between Azerbaijan and Armenia" [13].

Despite the fact that the museums of the occupied territories lost their buildings, almost all of their collections, household goods and exhibition equipment, they were not abolished as legal entities, and their staff was not dissolved. "Refugee museums continue to be funded by the Ministry of Culture, conduct their collecting and other activities, they have been allocated temporary premises, and salaries continue to be paid to the employees of these museums [14].

A special law was passed to strengthen the protection and qualitative replenishment of the country's museum fund, which has been forming since 1919, significantly improve the broad-vector activities of museums (there are 231 of them today), and create new ones, including private ones. The Law "On Museums" (2000) is an effective document regulating the relationship between the state and museums, defining their duties and functions, benefits and powers, precisely formulating the rules of activity and the rights of museums, contributing to the protection, preservation, development and enrichment of the museum fund and strengthening the social protection of museum workers [7, 2004].

Thus, it can be stated that the museum occupies an important place in the international cultural cooperation of Azerbaijan, which have a positive impact on the diplomatic and cultural image of the country.

References

1. Əliyev İ. Mədəni dəyərləri qorumaq siyasətimizin əsas məqsədidir// Azərbaycan qəz.. 12.04.2009
2. Абдуллаева С.Н. Культура Азербайджана в современном мире. Баку: Нурлан, 2007.
3. Александров А.А. Международное сотрудничество в сфере культурного наследия. М.: Проспект, 2010.
4. Алиева С.А. Основные черты культурной политики Азербайджана. URL: <http://www.jurnal.org/articles/2009/kult6.html>
5. Газета «Азербайджан». 9 августа 2003 г., № 181
6. Камминс А. Всемирное наследие и партнерства музеев // Информационный бюллетень ИКОМ России. 2007. № 3.
7. Курьер ЮНЕСКО. 2000-2010.
8. Мерфи Б. История музейного посредничества // Новости ИКОМ. 2006. № 3.
9. Раджабли А.А. Международные связи России. Баку: Китаб адеми, 2005.
10. Рыбак К.Е. Музейное право: международно-правовые аспекты. М.: Юристь, 2005.
11. Cultural Heritage Disaster Preparedness and Response: International Symposium Proceedings Salar Jung Museum Hyderabad, India 23-27 November 2003. ICOM. 2003 // <http://iram.museum/disasterjpreparedness/book/index.html>
12. <http://icom.museum/membership.html>
13. <http://www.azerbaijanfoundation.az/rus/news> (Миссия ЮНЕСКО) 15 сент. 2009
14. <http://www.mct.gov.az>
15. <http://www.unesco.org>